

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT IN GRAHANI WSR TO IBS: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS) is a chronic functional gastrointestinal disorder often exacerbated by psychological factors such as anxiety. In Ayurveda, this condition can be correlated to Grahani with predominant Vata involvement aggravated by Manasika bhavas. This case report highlights the role of Ayurvedic interventions in managing anxiety induced IBS. **Method:** A 51 yrs male patient presenting with recurrent abdominal discomfort, irregular bowel habits (Muhurbaddha, muhurshithil and apakwa malapravritti), abdominal bloating, and associated anxiety was evaluated through Ayurvedic diagnostic parameters including assessment of Agni, Vata-vikriti, and Manasika dosha involvement. Management was carried out using Shamana chikitsa address both gastrointestinal imbalance and anxiety. Supportive

measures such as panchkarma therapies, Vata shamaka dietary modifications, and simple breath regulation practices were incorporated. **Result:** After treatment Marked improvement was observed in abdominal pain, frequency of loose stools, bloating, and overall bowel regularity within 3–4 weeks. Anxiety symptoms reduced noticeably with improved sleep and appetite. **Discussion:** The case demonstrates that Ayurvedic management by addressing both Sharira and Manasika components can effectively reduce symptoms of anxiety induced IBS. Integrating shamana and panchkarma therapies may offer a holistic and safe approach in such psychosomatic conditions.

KEYWORDS: Grahani, Anxiety, Gastrointestinal disorder, Panchkarma.

A. INTRODUCTION

Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS) is a chronic functional gastrointestinal disorder often exacerbated by psychological factors such as anxiety. In Ayurveda, this condition can be correlated to Grahani with predominant Vata involvement aggravated by Manasika bhavas. This case report highlights the role of Ayurvedic interventions in managing anxiety induced IBS.

B. CASE REPORT

Present complaints: A 38 yrs male patient who was working in IT sector visited APM ayurved hospitals with complaints of Irregular bowl habits (muhurbaddha muhurpichil and apakwa malpravruti) since 5 yrs abdominal bloating aggravated due to anxiety.

Associated complaints: This was associated with passing mucus along with stools occasionally since a year intermittent abdominal discomfort and loss of appetite since few months

Treatment history: Patient taken allopathic medication for years but it gives temporary relief only patient visited our institute for ayurvedic management

k/c/o: NAD

S/H/O: NAD

HETU(NIDAN): Irregular eating habits, prolong sitting work, mansik hetu like stress.

Patient Examination

Asthavidha pariksha:

Nadi: vaatapittaj saam

Mala: 4-6times per day pichil kaphapatan, apakva malpravruti aggravated due to anxiety time not fixed Mutra: 7-10 / day prakrut

Jivha: saam lipta

Shabda: prakrut

Sparsha: anushna

Drik: prakrut

Akruti: madhyam

C. General examination

Vitals stable

General condition good

Per abdominal: distention, aadhmaan no pain

D. Diagnostic Criteria for IBS

The case diagnosed as vataja grahani based on symptoms explain in our classical texts

The case was diagnosed as irritable bowel syndrome using Manning's criteria as below.

Mannings criteria	Criteria satisfied by patient
Looser stool	+
More frequent stool at pain onsets	
Pain relief with defecation	
Abdominal distension	+
Mucus per rectum	+
Feeling of incomplete evacuation	+

E. Treatment

treatment	duration	procedure	medicines
Pachan internal medicines	22/10/2025 to 01/11/2025	h	Hinavasthak churna 3gms thrice a day before food Panchamruta parpati 1 tab thrice a day Takrarishta 20 ml twice a day Bramhi+ aswagandha + jatamansi 1gm thrice a day
Panchan along with shodhan	02 /11/2025 TO 10/11/2025	<p>Sarvanga abhagya : dashmool tail</p> <p>Baspha swedan: dashmool kwatha</p> <p>Yoga basti : 1) Niruha takra basti 650ml Kwata=musta shunthi bilwa mocharas 300ml</p> <p>1. kalka =shatavhadi Prakshep =takra 300ml</p> <p>2) Anuvasan basti : sahachar tail 120ml</p> <p>• Shirodhara : bramhi jatamansi siddha til tail timing 20mins to 60 min increase gradually</p>	All the above medicines continue along with panchkarma

F. Follow UP

- **Patient Assessed Outcome of Subjective Parameters**

Symptoms	Before treatment	After treatment	
		After 15 days	After 45 days
Frequency of defecation	5-6 times a day	2-4 times a day	1-3 times a day
Stool consistence	semisolid	Semisolid occasionally	normal solid (rarely semisolid)
Stool with mucus	Present	occasionally	absent
Abdominal distension	present	mild	Very rarely
Feeling of incomplete evacuation	present	mild	absent
appetite	poor	improved	good
anxiety	moderate	mild	mild

G. DISCUSSION

The management of anxiety-induced irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) requires a combined approach addressing both the gastrointestinal dysfunction and the underlying manasika (psychological) factors.

PHASE 1: DEEPAN PACHAN CHIKITSA

The patient with anxiety-induced IBS showed Vata aggravation and disturbed Agni. Initial 7-day Shamana therapy with Hingvastak Churna, Shutshekar Ras, Takrarishta, and Brahmi–Ashwagandha Churna helped

- reduce aadhaman,
- regulate digestion,
- calm anxiety.
- removes strotorodha

PHASE II- PANCHAKARMA TREATMENT

Sarvanga Abhyanga with warm medicated oil promoted Vata-shamana and neuromuscular relaxation.

Bashpa Swedana improved circulation, aided Ama clearance, and softened doshas for Basti.

Niruha Basti with Takra was chosen for its Grahi, Deepana-Pachana and Vata-Pitta pacifying action, especially beneficial in IBS with loose stools and anxiety.

Anuvasana Basti with Sahachar Taila nourished Vata, relieved colonic dryness, and stabilized bowel movement

Shirodhara with Brahmi-siddha Tila Taila had a significant calming effect on manovaha srotas, reducing anxiety, restlessness, and promoting stable gut function

H. After Panchakarma Follow UP

PHASE III- RASAYAN CHIKITSA

- Praval Panchamruta
prescribed for its Pittashamak and gut-soothing effects.its also provide agnideepan slowly
- Moravala: Pittashamaka & Rasayana due to Amla Madhur rasa and shita virya Madhur vipak, It pacifies Pitta and acts as a mild Rasayana, improving tissue nourishment and overall digestive resilience.
- Brahma Rasayan : enhanced mental calmness, improved sleep quality, and supported long-term stress resilience can be an essential factor in anxiety triggered IBS we also suggest patient some breathing exercises, meditation and core muscle exercises which helps to gives long term relief

I. CONCLUSION

The integrated Ayurvedic approach combining Shamana therapy, Panchakarma, and follow-up Rasayanas provided marked relief in anxiety-induced IBS by restoring Agni, balancing Vata, and improving both gut function and mental calmness.

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